

DOI: Will get Assigned Shortly.

ABSTRACT

Using descriptive-survey design, this paper focused on identifying the professional index, leadership manifestations, appraise their relationship, and design a leadership development plan for enhanced leadership practices of secondary school administrators. Data analysis revealed that majority of the secondary school administrators in the Division of Biliran are men, between the ages of 40 – 59 years, master’s degree holders, with NEAP certifications, with less than 10 years of experience as administrator, performing very satisfactorily, and without outstanding accomplishments. Leadership manifestations were occasionally performed. Significant relationship was noted between the administrators’ education, NEAP certification, experience as school administrator, outstanding accomplishment, and their leadership manifestations. School leaders must therefore plan for leadership development through education, NEAP certification, gaining relevant experience, and outstanding accomplishments to enhance their leadership manifestations in schools.

KEYWORDS: Professional Index, Leadership Manifestations, Secondary School Administrators.

INTRODUCTION

In the absence of leadership, goal accomplishment and school effectiveness is never guaranteed. Recent failures in solving problems, decision-making and in establishing organizational solidarity are just some of the challenges in the pursuit of refining leadership manifestations of both existing and would-be leaders.

Davis, et.al. (2005) elaborated that school administrators play a vital role in setting the direction for successful schools, but existing knowledge on the best ways to prepare and develop highly qualified candidates is sparse. This idea was supported by Sebring and Bryk (2000) when they averred that leadership manifestations or behaviors of the school administrator have influence on all aspects of the learning community, which leads to school success. In view of Cheng, et.al. (as cited by Sharma, 2011), the educational leader is challenged to create the culture of quality that penetrates to the smallest elements, processes and the systems of an institution. It is likewise viewed that an educational institution degenerates, or maintains status quo, or rises to prominence with a change of leaders.

In the Philippine setting, as the public educational system draws near 2015 which is the deadline of meeting Education for All (EFA) goals, it is also marching towards the most demanding ages of the 21st century- ‘behooving all educational leaders to reflect, analyze, plan and take action in order to cope with multifaceted changes in the borderless marketplace.’ For this matter, effective school managers are expected to be academically goal oriented and supervise instructional and co-curricular practices accordingly (Delagoza 1998). Moreover, Clemente (1996) emphasized the need to identify and develop education managers fit to pilot schools into the 21st Century.

Professional index of individuals are given little consideration that later bring about poor management styles and performances of existing executives. Increased scholastic demands and technological advancements have resulted in the need for better-trained and qualified school administrators. Determining what the profiles and qualifications of school administrators should be to develop these critical leadership manifestations is a great challenge today. Most studies have focused on leadership styles and traits, rather than leadership manifestations.

The present researcher, thus, intends to fill this gap by investigating the administrators' professional index variables, namely: sex, age, educational attainment, NEAP certification, experience, performance rating, and outstanding accomplishments in relation to the various categories of the leadership manifestations of secondary school administrators in Biliran Division as perceived by the teachers; with the intention to offer a leadership development plan which might be useful to school administrators and officials of the Department of Education (DepED) in its efforts to enhance the administration of secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive-survey design was used in this study. Using survey questionnaires, data concerning professional index and leadership manifestations of secondary school administrators were gathered. The research instruments used were the "Professional Index Sheets" accomplished by the administrator-respondents, and the modified "Leader Manifestations Checklist" originally designed by the Collegiate Project Services, which was accomplished by the teacher-respondents comprised of 60 items that are clustered under the following 9 categories of leadership manifestations: (a) communicating purpose and direction; (b) communicating and behaving according to values; (c) showing enthusiasm for people; (d) instilling in people the belief they are powerful; (e) being consistent in the face of adversity; (f) planning and leading change; (g) releasing potential and energy; (h) creating a flexible and "ready-for-change" culture; and (i) developing leaders in the organization. The information obtained greatly aided in proposing leadership development plan needed in solving prevailing as well as emerging leadership difficulties.

There were 35 public secondary school administrators (school heads and department heads) and 76 teacher-raters from 20 secondary schools in the Division of Biliran who participated in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings revealed in this study were summarized as follows:

Professional Index of the Administrators

Of the 35 secondary school administrators in Biliran Division, 19 (54.29%) were male and 16 (45.71%) were female. There were 13 (37.14%) administrators in age group 50 – 59 years, 13 (37.1%) in age group 40 – 49 years, 5 (14.29%) in age group 39 years and below; and only 4 (11.43%) were 60 years and above. There were 17 (48.57%) of them who were master's degree holder, 16 (45.71%) have completed their academic requirements leading to a master's degree, 1 (2.86%) holds a doctoral degree, and 1 (2.86%) has complete academic requirements for a doctoral degree. It was found that 22 (62.86%) have NEAP certification, while 13 (37.14%) have none. In their administrative position, 32 (91.43%) are tenured for 10 years and below, 2 (5.71%) between 11 to 20 years, and 1 (2.86%) percent for 21 years and above. On the basis of performance ratings obtained, 29 (82.86%) were very satisfactory, 6 (17.14%) were outstanding, and no one was rated satisfactory, unsatisfactory, or poor. As observed, majority of the administrators 30 in numbers (85.71%) have no outstanding accomplishment reported in their entire leadership career, whereas 2 (5.71%) administrators have division level citations, 1 (2.86%) has district/school level, 1 (2.86%) has regional level, and 1 (2.86%) has national level recognition (Table 1).

Table 1. Professional Index of School Administrators

Professional Index		<i>f</i>	%
Sex	Male	19	54.29
	Female	16	45.71
Total		35	100
Age	60 years and above	4	11.43
	50 - 59 years	13	37.14
	40 - 49 years	13	37.14
	39 years and below	5	14.29
Total		35	100
Educational Attainment			
	Doctoral Degree	1	2.86

C.A.R. for Doctoral Degree	1	2.86
Master's Degree	17	48.57
C.A.R. for Master's Degree	16	45.71
Bachelor's Degree		
Total	35	100
NEAP Certification		
with Certification	22	62.86
without Certification	13	37.14
Total	35	100
Experience as School Administrator		
21 years and above	1	2.86
11 - 20 years	2	5.71
10 years and below	32	91.43
Total	35	100
Performance Rating		
Outstanding	6	17.14
Very Satisfactory	29	82.86
Satisfactory		
Unsatisfactory		
Poor		
Total	35	100
Outstanding Accomplishments		
International Level		
National Level	1	2.86
Regional Level	1	2.86
Division Level	2	5.71
District/School Level	1	2.86
None	30	85.71
Total	35	100

Leadership Manifestations of the Administrators

Secondary school administrators were subsequently rated to be occasionally engaged in manifestations that are known to be characteristics of effective leaders with an overall mean of 3.46. Table 2 sums up the Leadership Manifestations of School Administrators and the corresponding interpretations.

Table 2. Summary of the Leadership Manifestations of School Administrators

Leadership Manifestations	WM	Interpretation
A. Communicating Purpose (Mission) and Direction (Vision)	3.52	Often
B. Communicating and Behaving According to Values	3.42	Occasionally
C. Showing Enthusiasm for People	3.51	Often
D. Instilling in People the Belief that they are Powerful	3.53	Often
E. Being Consistent in the Face of Adversity	3.45	Occasionally

F. Planning and Leading Change	3.38	Occasionally
G. Releasing Potential and Energy	3.42	Occasionally
H. Creating a Flexible and “Ready-for-Change” Culture	3.44	Occasionally
I. Developing Leaders in the Organization	3.51	Often
OVER - ALL MEAN	3.46	Occasionally

Relationship of Variables

The result showed that there is a significant relationship between the administrators’ professional index in terms of: educational attainment, NEAP certification, experience as school administrator, and outstanding accomplishments; and their leadership behaviors in which the χ^2 - computed values of 19.75, 16.14, 19.65, and 30.92 are greater than χ^2 - tabular values of 16.92, 7.82, 12.50, and 21.03; with degrees of freedom of 9, 3, 6, and 12 respectively at 0.05 level of significance.

Other variables such as sex, age, and performance rating did not yield significant results whose χ^2 - computed values of 2.54, 7.92, and 3.41 are less than the χ^2 - tabular values of 7.82, 16.92, and 7.82; with degrees of freedom of 3, 9, and 3 respectively whose level of significance are also set at 0.05 (Table 3).

Table 3. The Relationship between Professional Index and Leadership Manifestations of School Administrators

Variables	df	Leadership Manifestations (χ^2)		Decision
		CV	TV	
Sex	3	2.54	7.82	H ₀ accepted
Age	9	7.92	16.92	H ₀ accepted
Educational Attainment	9	19.75	16.92	H ₀ rejected
NEAP Certification	3	16.14	7.82	H ₀ rejected
Experience as School Administrator	6	19.65	12.50	H ₀ rejected
Performance Rating	3	3.41	7.82	H ₀ accepted
Outstanding Accomplishment	12	30.92	21.03	H ₀ rejected

$\alpha = 0.05$

CONCLUSION

On account of the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that secondary school administrators in the Division of Biliran were generally perceived to be occasionally engaged in critical leadership manifestations that are known to be effective in setting direction and inspiring others in the organization. This further indicates that there are still opportunities for improvement in some aspects of leadership particularly in communicating and behaving according to values, being consistent in the face of adversity, planning and leading change, releasing potential and energy, and creating a flexible and “ready-for-change” culture.

Improved leadership is assumed feasible as supported by the behavioral theory of leadership, on which this study was founded that is focused on developing leadership skills rather than looking for inborn traits as great leaders are made, not born.

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